

Analysis of The Stages of Personality Development and The Implications for The Process of Education

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<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4054101>

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to undertake an analysis of personality development features and their implications for the process of education. The significance of this exercise is to facilitate the adequate adaptation of the teaching and learning process to personality characteristics in order to optimize learning in the classroom. The paper pointed out various personality stages of development and their characteristics. Having analyzed the personality development features it is further pointed out that the teacher stands best to promote learning in the process of education by taking cognizance of the identified individual personality differences and adapt as follows: the lesson plan to take advantage of the personality types, teaching methods to suit the personality types in the teaching and learning situation, select instructional content and materials suitable for the learners' cognitive, social and psychomotor characteristics, evaluation strategies to suit the stages of personality development of learners. The foregoing educational implications of the stages of development require that teachers must be appropriately trained for effective participation in the various stages of managing learners.

Key words: Personality Development, Educational Adaptation, Classroom Management, Instructional Evaluation

Introduction

Generally speaking, human personality encompasses the unique disposition associated with individuals which also defines their attributes such as the attitude, emotional, social, mental and physical aspects. Understanding the characterizations of human personality has been a major preoccupation of psychologists for ages. Accordingly, knowledge about human personality and its development has been well documented even as it continues to evolve. It is significant to also state that as a versatile and very useful field of study and knowledge, it is imperative that all social services providers, particularly in education, sports and industry among others, need a deep knowledge of human personality as well as the capacity to deploy the optimization of it to their respective goal attainment.

The particular purpose of this paper is to undertake an overview of the development of human personality and the implications for the process of education.

The foregoing task would be conducted as follows: Meaning of human personality, components of human personality, personality types, psychosocial theory of personality, educational implications of personality development, conclusion and recommendations.

Meaning of Personality

Personality has been variously defined by many scholars. Meyers (2008) stated that researchers have defined personality in terms of stable and enduring behavioural patterns. Accordingly, Eysenck (1963) sees personality as the more or less stable and enduring organization of a person's character, temperament, intellect and physique which determine the person's unique adjustment to his environment. Elaborating further, Meyers (2008) viewed personality as an individual's characteristic pattern of thinking, feeling and acting. Similarly, Ogu, Agbanusi and Umeasiegbu (2008) have described personality as the totality of self and the reaction to situation at any given time.

From the foregoing, it can be concluded that the term 'personality' is a combination of an individual's emotional, intellectual and moral qualities, which makes the individual a unique person as highlighted in the opening session of this paper.

Components of Personality

Components of a child's personality include

- i. Temperament
- ii. Environment and
- iii. Character

These components as put forward by Laberge (2005) and Santrock (2011) are discussed below;

Temperament: This is a natural disposition of an individual, which is seen in the way the individual reacts to situations, think or feels. Temperament could also be referred to as an individual's inborn traits. According to Laberge (2005), genes which control the development of the nervous system are also responsible for controlling the individual's behaviour. This, in Santrock's (2011) opinion, explains why children respond in different ways to situations. According to him, some children are active while others are calm. Some are very embracing or friendly while others fuss and fret.

Environment: Environmental factors also known as "nature" play a very important role in the development of a child's personality. Laberge (2005) opined that many psychologists have argued that temperament and environment impact most on a child's personality development, but there is still controversy as to which factor ranks higher. Laberge asserted, however, that parents, who understand how to adapt their parenting style to the particular temperament of their child, achieve best in providing guidance towards the successful development of their child's personality.

Character: Laberge (2005) opined that character, which is an individual's set of emotional, cognitive and behavioural patterns, depends on inborn traits and early experiences, which determine how an individual reacts to situations. Character is also said to depend on an individual's moral development.

In the next section of this paper, the nature of human personality is further discussed.

Personality Types

Personality types are common labels which help to differentiate one individual from another, (Odebunmi, 1992). Personality types are also viewed by Meyers (2008) as the predominant behavioural modes of individuals. Furthermore, Jung (1993) had earlier proposed the extrovert versus introvert personality types based on his clinical observations. He theorized that individuals fall into one of the two categories, either an individual is introverted or extroverted. Beside these two categories, Jung also came up with several additional concepts, which Ogu, Agbanusi and Umeasiegbe (2008) summarized the individual differences associated with each human being are attributable to the variations in personality types as follows:

- i. Extroverted Sensing
- ii. Introverted Sensing
- iii. Extroverted Intuition
- iv. Introverted Intuition
- v. Extroverted Thinking
- vi. Introverted Thinking
- vii. Extroverted Feeling
- viii. Introverted Feeling

In addition, Ogu, Agbanusi and Umeasiegbe (2008) stated that, Jung's work on personality was further expanded by Katherine Briggs and Isabel Briggs, with the later bringing Jung's work on personality to limelight. According to them, personality theory, today, is developed along four primary categories, namely;

- i. Individual's flow of energy
- ii. Mode of information processing
- iii. Mode of decision making process
- iv. Day to day lifestyle

They assert that within each of these categories, individuals prefer to be either

- i. Extroverted or Introverted
- ii. Sensitive or Intuitive
- iii. Thinking or Feeling
- iv. Judging or Perceiving

Jung's model enables us understand in significant ways the nature of human personality, as it attempted to explain why people behave the way they do. Many of the theories in use today derived some fundamental formulations, techniques and impetus from Jung's personality theory. In spite of these observations, however, Erikson's psychosocial theory of human development is well acknowledged as a further relevant authority building on Freud's psychoanalytic theories in advancing our knowledge of human personality development.

Psychosocial Theory of Human Personality Development

Sigmund Freud (1856-1931) was the originator of psychoanalytic theory of personality development. Freud grew up in a time of great scientific progress, which influenced the

development of his psychological theories. His conception of people led to his idea that human motivation was influenced by unconscious sources of energy. There are many psychoanalytic theories, which originated from Freud's theory. This paper focuses on the psychosocial theory propounded by Erik Erikson (1950-1963), which is an extension of Freudian's thought. Unlike Freud, who talked about five psychosexual stages of personality development, Erikson discussed psychosocial stages. The eight stages of Erikson's theory as summarized by Laberge (2005), Tuckman and Monetti (2011) and Mclead (2013) are briefly discussed below:

❖ **Infancy (Trust VS Mistrust)**

The first stage of Erikson's theory focuses on the infant, in which the child develops trust or mistrust based on the child's experiences. During this period, which is the first two years of life, the child sticks to the stimuli he is exposed to and which shapes his trait on the continuum of trust and mistrust. Myers (2008) asserted that if the child's needs are dependably met, the child develops a sense of basic trust. On the other hand a child that is not well nurtured becomes insecure and learns "basic mistrust" (Laberge, 2005).

❖ **Toddlerhood (Autonomy VS Shame and Doubt)**

In this second stage of development, which ranges from eighteen months to three or four years, children desire to assert themselves and are willing to explore the environment, using their hands to do things on their own, such as choosing the toys to play with, dressing themselves, walking away from their parents or care-givers etc. According to Tuckman and Monetti (2011), if care-givers or parents are over controlling or over protective, the children will be faced with defeat, which results in feelings of doubt and shame. On the other hand, the children will develop feeling of autonomy if allowed to assert and explore their environment.

❖ **Early Childhood (Initiative VS Guilt)**

This is the preschool age, which falls between age three to five. During this period, children are very interactive and are very playful. Tuckman and Monetti (2011) assert that this period, is a stage of play and curiosity, of powerful impulse to explore and express. If children are given the opportunity to play, initiate activities and interact with other children, they develop a sense of initiative. However, Tuckman and Monetti (2011) stated that children develop a sense of guilt if their tendencies or impulses are thwarted or frustrated by adults.

❖ **School Age (Industry (Competence) VS Inferiority)**

This stage commences from five years to twelve years. Children at this stage are willing to learn formal skills and participate in all school experiences to develop their psychomotor, cognate and affective attributes. Tuckman and Monetti (2011) opined that children seek to win approval or recognition by producing and accomplishing things. Mclead (2005) stated that children, whose initiatives are encouraged and reinforced, feel industrious and confident in their ability to accomplish a task, while the reverse is the case if unsuccessful. They develop a sense of inferiority and doubt their own abilities to achieve goals.

❖ **Adolescence (Identity VS Confusion)**

This is the stage of transition from children to adulthood and it is within the age of twelve to eighteen years. There is a quest for relevance by the individual, independence and assertion of one's identity. There is also a trait of turbulence, disobedience and peer group influence. Myers

(2008) viewed this period as a major stage in development. According to him, some adolescents have earlier forge their identity either by taking on their parents' values and expectations or adopting the identity defined in opposition to parents but inconformity with their peers. In addition, Myers stipulates further, that the adolescents must integrate many "fragmented selves" into a coherent consistent and unified whole (identity). Failure in this respect, the individual may suffer role confusion.

❖ **Young Adulthood (Intimacy VS Isolation)**

Unlike Freud's theory, which stopped at the fifth stage of adolescence, according to Myers (2008), Erikson, expanded his theory to accommodate the young adulthood, middle adulthood and late adulthood. Myers views young adulthood, from age twenty to forty, as a crucial turning point with the choice of intimacy on one hand or isolation on the other hand. To Myers, young adults must struggle to form close relationship and to gain the capacity for intimate love or suffer emotional isolation if unsuccessful.

❖ **Adulthood (Generativity VS Stagnation)**

This is the stage referred to as middle adulthood, from age forty to sixty-five. Laberge (2005) views this stage as a period, when individuals continue to build their lives, establish their careers, focus on their own family as well as contributing meaningfully to society through raising their own children and being productive at work. Mclead (2013) stated that care is the virtue achieved when this stage is handled successfully, while failure to handle this stage results in stagnation and the individual feels unproductive.

❖ **Ego (Integrity VS Despair)**

This is a period of late adulthood, from sixty-five and above. In this stage, the older adult reflects back on his or her past life, to see whether he or she is successful or not. Laberge (2005) asserts that, older adults who are unsuccessful at this age, would feel they wasted their lives and would be full of many regrets. This situation, according to Laberge, leads to feelings of bitterness and despair. However, if the individual is successful, a sense of satisfaction and integrity is developed. The foregoing presentation has portrayed an overview of personality development and the next section of this paper attempts to examine the implications for the process of education.

Educational Implications of Personality Development

The focus in the preceding section of this paper has been on the analysis of personality development. This has made possible the elucidation of human personality characteristics as they evolve in vertically ordered manner from infancy to adulthood.

These stages of personality development have implications for the process of education. In this section of this paper, the focus shifts to analysis of the educational implications of the personality characteristics already presented.

The education process is principally concerned with ensuring effective learning in the classroom. This involves the following:

- (1) planning for instruction from a given syllabus
- (2) planning the lesson
- (3) presentation of the lesson and classroom management

(4) evaluation of learning outcomes

It suffices to state here that the process of education would be most successful and productive of goal attainment by its adaptation to stages of personality development. The effectiveness of the educational processes is inevitably contingent on the extent they are adapted to the personality characteristics of those involved at the various levels of learning.

The teacher in particular who is the manager of the educational processes outlined above need to be constantly reminded about this reality.

Toddlers and pre-school children are yet to understand themselves and their environment in any significant way. At this stage, however, education can play a role in their quest to have a sense of who they are in concrete terms. The teacher could help children at this stage to learn better by properly structuring the environment to be devoid of obstacles, infused with exploratory gadgets with close monitoring and reinforcement of appropriate behaviour.

At the stage of adolescent that is between 12-18 years, there is a desire to show one's identity and a personality that depicts vitality and high energy levels. It is incumbent on educators to prime learning experiences that enable learners to demonstrate their competences and absorb their energies as well. Furthermore, learning experiences and tasks must be organized from simple to complex to give the learners a sense of success and achievement. In the same vein, the appropriate responses to tasks by learners must be promptly rewarded or reinforced by the teachers. In another perspective, the curriculum need to take cognizance of the natural environment in which it is to be experienced so as to incorporate materials that are familiar to the learners. One other point about the curriculum for this group of learners is that flexibility is crucial. Flexibility would make it possible for learners of different personality types to find something interesting and suitable and hence, optimize their potentials. This is a way of ensuring that no one is left behind in the learning process.

On another significant note, the reality of difference in personality types in classroom situation makes it mandatory for the teachers to adapt instructional styles to suit the learners. Some may require modified instructional cues to bring them to threshold, while others could require outright individualized instruction to enable them reach their learning goals.

Graphic illustration examples of possible adaptations of the educational processes to personality development characteristics are provided in the table below.

Personality Development and Educational Adaptations

STAGES OF PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT	CHARACTERISTICS	SUGGESTED EDUCATIONAL ADAPTATIONS
Early Childhood (3-6 yrs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Active play ❖ Interactive ❖ Exploratory ❖ Short Attention Span 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Teachers should make children the centre of learning, the teacher is only to work as a guide and facilitator. ❖ Provide didactic materials that involve sensory experiences and are self-correcting e.g. variety of toys, building blocks, letter words, mathematics, language, music, art etc. that are age appropriate for the children. ❖ Provide concrete examples of things from the child's environment that the child can understand, see, hear, feel etc. ❖ The teacher should use play method, plan varieties of play activities (both indoor and outdoor play), use story-telling and demonstration methods. ❖ Structure the learning environment to be comfortable and devoid of harmful objects

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Encourage team work among the children ❖ Modeling and role-acting. Children learn by imitation.
School Age (6-12 yrs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Artistic ❖ Seek teachers approval ❖ Show willingness to learn and gain knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Create a safe and enabling learning environment ❖ The teacher should always state clearly the objectives of the lesson. ❖ Apply varying modes of lesson presentation e.g. project method, activity method, learning by doing etc. ❖ Use of modeling. Children learn best by imitation. ❖ Make the lesson very interesting by adding a moderate sense of humor. ❖ Take the children out on excursion or field trips to places of interest. ❖ Use appropriate motivational tools e.g. tangible and intangible rewards. ❖ Simplify the learning materials. Instruction should move from known to unknown. ❖ Evaluate the children regularly and provide feedback to them.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ The teacher must understand the special needs of the children. ❖ The teacher should use mild punishment where appropriate.
Adolescent (12-18 yrs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Assertiveness ❖ Exercising their independence ❖ Tendency to disobey parents ❖ Vulnerability to peer influence ❖ Vitality and high energy level ❖ Sexual feelings ❖ Mood swings ❖ Risk taking tendency ❖ Exploratory lifestyle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Create a pleasant classroom environment ❖ Encourage active participation in class work ❖ The teacher should regularly give the adolescents take home assignment. ❖ Engage children in creative activities ❖ Encourage peer tutoring. ❖ Be effective at class management. ❖ Teachers should be supportive. ❖ Should show the adolescents love and warm acceptance. ❖ Teachers should let them know behaviour that is appropriate and inappropriate. ❖ Should use behavioural techniques to correct maladaptive behaviour or refer the adolescent to the school counsellor if need be.

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Based on the foregoing, it cannot be too much to conjure that the process of education could profit most by a deliberate effort at profiling the personality types in learning situations and ensure that the curriculum, instructional process, evaluation and instructional materials are all in harmony. Perhaps, this is the key to improving the quality of public education in Nigeria.

Conclusion

This paper attempts to provide an overview of personality types. The information provided has possibly enabled us to broaden our knowledge of the varieties of human and the way they evolve. It should be obvious that human personality is the bedrock of human activities and effectiveness. Consequently, its development and nurturing is critical to all aspects of human endeavour. Also, a particular attention has been focused on the implication of human personality for the process of education. The sum total of the arguments pursued is that the process of education at all times must take advantage of, and be adapted to the personality profiles in the learning situations.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were further offered:

1. Social Institutions including the school and family should provide a conducive environment for proper development of human personality.
2. Teachers should provide enabling environment that suits the varying personality characteristics of children in a learning situation.
3. Each individual owns a responsibility to himself to fully understand his own personality and positively develop capacity to manage and deploy the attributes to productive endeavours.
4. The process of education and human personality must work in harmony for success to be achieved.
5. It is recommended that continuous research should be conducted by scholars to explore and shed more light on the relationship between personality development and the education process.

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